

MANAGEMENT OF MODERN MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF NATIONAL GOODS IN COMPETITIVE MARKETS

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Annotation: The article analyzes the main purpose of the work carried out by the state to regulate economic processes to ensure a competitive advantage in the development of competitive markets. In the rapid development of the economy, every producer strives to excel in the competitive struggle. The fact that the basis of economic reforms in our country is aimed at the production of ready-made competitive products, effective management of marketing activities in business and increase the volume of exports of products also confirms these views. One of the most important social policies in the country's economy is to ensure employment and improve living standards. Therefore, in the context of the development of competitive markets in our country, the management of marketing activities in business, the creation and development of a competitive environment in manufacturing enterprises are discussed today as important.

Keywords: competition, entrepreneurship, competitiveness, marketing, charter capital, concept, cooperation.

One of the areas that the President pays great attention to today is the economy, as a result of which economic reforms are being carried out to increase the competitiveness of national goods in the domestic consumer goods market. Proof of this is the creation of free economic zones and clusters for the preparation of products in some regions of the country, created to support entrepreneurs. The head of state is creating a legal framework to support entrepreneurs, the production of competitive products and entrepreneurship. As a proof of our opinion, in the third direction of the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, approved by the Decree of the President of February 7, 2017, "... a fundamentally new product and mastering the types of technologies, thereby ensuring the competitiveness of national goods in domestic and foreign markets"¹. Drawing the right conclusions from these tasks, during his official visits to the Republic of

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021." - Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017 www.lex.uz.

Karakalpakstan and the regions, the head of state stressed the need to establish enterprises producing national goods in the region, develop competitive markets and increase the competitiveness of goods² emphasizes.

Another legal basis is the adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further liberalize trade and develop competition in commodity markets" to provide producers in domestic markets with the necessary goods and create a healthy competitive environment in the commodity market. development also has a special content, as it is important in ensuring the competitiveness of manufactured products³ (3).

According to the decree, there are a number of problems that hinder the expansion of trade turnover of entrepreneurs, the supply of domestic markets and producers with the necessary goods, as well as the export of goods produced in the country, in particular:

development of wholesale trade, low level of supply of semi-finished products and industrial products for further processing, other goods on a "business-to-business" (B2B) basis is one of the main reasons for the increase in transaction costs of operating entities and the decline in the competitiveness of their products in foreign markets;

the slow introduction of futures, derivatives and other modern mechanisms of exchange trade, which protect entrepreneurs, especially agricultural producers, from the effects of adverse changes in market prices, limits the volume of transactions and the range of products offered for sale;

the high share of the state in the charter capital of trade entities, the persistence of outdated restrictions in the field of retail trade and services hinder the consistent development of a competitive environment in these areas;

Lack of systematic work on informing producers and consumers, including foreign consumers, about the types and volumes of products in high demand in the country, as well as foreign hindering the development of production cooperation with manufacturers.

In our opinion, the development of wholesale trade, increasing the range and volume of high-demand products in the country, increasing the competitiveness of goods in domestic and foreign markets, expanding research, marketing research, the widespread use of modern marketing concepts.

² Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Serving the people, serving the interests of the people is the main criterion of leadership. - // People's speech, April 13, 2017, №73 (6767).

³ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further liberalize trade and develop competition in commodity markets." - // People's speech, October 31, 2018, № 225 (7183)

The concept of marketing is a system of market management, principles, goals, aimed at achieving a specific goal of the enterprise and a clear way of operating in the market. Enterprises of different forms of ownership try to gain an advantage over competitors in the conditions of competitive markets and use marketing concepts in doing so. Forming marketing concepts begins with choosing a competitive advantage. Entrepreneurs seek to achieve their strategic goals by using the competitive advantage they have chosen to grow their business.

The competitiveness of goods is assessed by indicators such as market share, demand dynamics, elasticity of demand. These factors include price and quality, efficiency of after-sales services, terms of delivery (time, type of payment, transportation costs) and consumption costs.

Consumer-oriented marketing, manufacturing, branding, sales, traditional marketing, socio-ethical marketing, and cross-market marketing concepts are used to increase market share and improve the quality of products and services. These concepts are one of the main areas of activity in the development of enterprises producing goods and services.

An important and primary goal of marketing is to find, attract, and increase the number of real consumers of the products they produce through the formation of a high level of consumer value. It is worth quoting Igor Mann: "The main task of marketing today is to find, develop and retain customers."⁴. From these considerations, it is clear that every company and entrepreneur must first decide what needs to serve the population. In service, companies do this by segmenting consumers. In today's fast-paced world, the concept of consumer-oriented marketing is also characterized by the choice of a specific target segment and its focus on high-quality, comprehensive services. It is well known that the concept of customer relationship marketing also plays an important role in this.

In addition to the concepts discussed above, there are a number of modern marketing concepts in place, as trends in competitive markets are changing very rapidly. It is necessary to apply modern marketing concepts such as innovative marketing, neutral marketing, logistics marketing, neuromarketing, digital marketing, B2B, B2S, interactive marketing, touch marketing, network marketing, interaction marketing, impression marketing, CRM. A new approach to understanding the concept of marketing is based on an integral relationship with the so-called target groups of potential customers of organizations from the

⁴ Igor Mann. Arithmetic marketing for beginners.-M.: Mann, Ivanov and Ferber, 2011.str.10.

strategic segment of the market. By researching the competitive market, dividing consumers into different groups and identifying strategic segments, the company saves available resources and achieves high results in subsequent contacts with existing and potential customers. So far, marketing activities in the country are not limited to the sale of manufactured products, but are characterized by a serious study of the needs and requirements of consumers and rapid adaptation.

In conclusion, it should be noted that modern marketing concepts in increasing the export potential of enterprises of various forms of ownership, producers and service enterprises, small industrial zones, small businesses, increasing the competitiveness of national goods. In use, the effective use of the principle of consumer orientation, not from the point of view of providers, but from the point of view of consumers, is important to use effective communication systems, creating convenience for consumers at the optimal cost.

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